

DEVELOPING OF TECHNICAL CREATIVITY IN FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

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Annotation The state policy in our country is aimed at forming people who are active, independent, goal-oriented, creative and responsible, able to successfully perform various vital roles in the modern pluralistic changing world. It is necessary to fundamentally change the paradigm. Only then can the main goal of education be considered comprehensive development of all subjects of the pedagogical process.

Key words: Technical creator, skill, responsible person, interactive methods. Innovative technologies, an aspiring creator, an active initiative person.

The 21st century promotes the issue of socio-economic development in the world, the accumulation of knowledge, skills, life experience and skills in the field that the young people want to occupy. This is largely determined by education, the development of the modern system of continuous education, and the level of professional competence of teachers. It is known that the development of the education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan is a priority task of the state and society.

The state policy in our country is aimed at forming people who are active, independent, goal-oriented, creative and responsible, able to successfully perform various life roles in the modern pluralistic changing world. For this, it is necessary to create new technologies of education and change its information paradigm. Only then can the main goal of education be defined as comprehensive development of all subjects of the pedagogical process.

Today, development as an alternative to the concept of teaching should be the main, essential concept of the modern education system. Because in educational

institutions, it is necessary to create such an environment and conditions that students become active subjects of the educational process, and the focus of attention of pedagogues is on the cognitive activity of students, that is, not teaching, but knowing to develop the process. The goal of education should be focused on the development of individual characteristics, abilities and skills, free from the method of enlightening learners, to form a free, creative person capable of defining and changing his future life strategy.

Educators have a special role in this. Because, as we would like, the formation of a well-rounded person depends on the life experiences, competences, knowledge levels of teachers, and how well they work on themselves.

Today, in addition to the above, pedagogues are required to know at least one foreign language and information-communication and pedagogical technologies. Erudition, methodical skills, and successful selection of educational technology are not enough for a teacher's efforts to be effective and practical. In this, the pedagogue's high-level speech skills, facial expressions, behavior in class, and dress code take an important place. Only then students will accept such pedagogues as a bright and unique person and take an example and "model" from him.

When thinking about the technical creativity of a teacher, it is necessary to find answers to a number of questions: creativity, what is creativity, what should a creative teacher be like. To find answers to the above questions, we turn to scientific literature and works of experts. For example, in the Encyclopedia of Pedagogy, creativity is defined as follows: "Creativity is striving for innovation, being able to analyze the latest achievements of science and technology, and to use them effectively in one's work, always working on oneself. Creativity is a conscious, goal-oriented, active activity of a person."

In our opinion, creativity is an activity related to the creation of new, original and improved material and spiritual values, the result of which is objectively or subjectively significant, and the improvement of existing ones. There are several

types of creativity. For example, scientific creativity, artistic creativity, pedagogical creativity, technical creativity, etc

In the course of their activities, teachers are not only engaged in pedagogical creativity, but also in artistic creativity, scientific creativity, and technical creativity. belongs to the system of methods. Today, pedagogical activities of teachers can be conventionally divided into creative and non-creative (non-creative) activities, and they are distinguished by a number of characteristics. For example:

- as a result, creativity is characterized by taking into account new, previously unknown innovations; "creativity" in practice gives a known, standard, serial copy (product);

- according to the method of implementation, in which creativity is unique in its movement towards the result, that is, it is manifested as the creation of a completely new method, or a certain combination of methods of action;

"lack of creativity" is characterized by the repeatability (pattern) of the method of achieving the result;

- according to its importance, creativity determines qualitatively different stages of the development of activity, and the quality of its direct driving force is also manifested. And lack of creativity is a means of quantitative accumulation of conditions for fundamental changes, that is, creativity.

A technical creative teacher is an innovator who strives to improve forms, methods and methods of educational work and to develop new ones; a person who can see a new problem even in an ordinary task, can formulate a creative task for students, and can actively involve them in independent research activities on solving and analyzing these tasks; its goal is not only to enrich students with knowledge, skills and qualifications system, but also to develop them mentally and intellectually, to prepare them for creative activities, to form various competencies in young people, and to effectively apply the elements of pedagogical artistry in the course of the lesson should be a guide.

It should be emphasized that today some teachers do not have aspects of pedagogical creativity. A number of reasons can be given for this:

teachers do not have love for students and pedagogical activities;

- lack of development of creative pedagogical skills in them;
- lack of desire for pedagogical creativity;
- unwillingness or inability to give up outdated and less effective forms and methods of educational work in class and extracurricular processes;
- low level of professional training;

In conclusion, it can be said that teachers should regularly work on themselves, be aware of new regulatory and legal documents related to the educational system and news in the field, constantly study advanced foreign experiences, learn from them the necessary. It is required to be able to apply them in the practice of education, to inculcate national and universal values in the minds of students.

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